

The design of a quasi-experimental study on sustainable work ability in health care organisations

Erik HA BEUNE^{1,2}, KI PROPER¹, AJ VAN DER BEEK¹, A BURDORF³

¹*Department of Public and Occupational Health, EMGO Institute for Health and Care Research, VU University Medical Centre, Amsterdam, The Netherlands*

²*Werxx, independent consulting firm, Voorhout, The Netherlands*

³*Department of Public Health, Erasmus MC, Rotterdam, The Netherlands*

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1. Background

Limited evidence is available on interventions to improve sustainable work ability in the health care sector. The aim of this paper is to describe the design of a study to evaluate an intervention aimed at improving sustainable work ability, health and productivity.

2. Methods

A quasi-experimental study was performed in five health care organisations. The intervention consisted of eight growth sessions for workers and additional training sessions for managers during a 6 months period aimed at improving personal and job resources to cope with work. Measurements were performed at baseline, and 12 months after baseline. At 6 months, the intervention group received an extra questionnaire with respect to the resources addressed in the intervention. Primary outcome measures are work ability, self-perceived health and productivity. Multilevel regression analyses will be performed to determine the effect of the intervention. Additionally, a cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analysis will be performed. A process evaluation will be performed to get insight into the participation in the intervention and to determine the changes in the resources addressed in the intervention.

3. Results

The expected results are an improvement in sustainable work ability, perceived health and productivity in health care organisations.

4. Conclusions

With this study insight will be given into the (cost-)effectiveness of a program aimed to improve sustainable work ability of health care workers. If (cost-)effective, future implementation of the intervention in the health care sector is recommended.